

REHABILITATION BASED SOCIETY MODEL AS THE FULFILLMENT OF CHILDS'S NEED EFFORT WITH DISABILITY

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Abstract

This study aims to formulate a rehabilitation based society model to the fulfillment of children need with disability in the village. This study uses the approach, Research and Development (R&D), because this study is a process to develop an education product. The product in this context is society rehabilitation model. In the implementation process, these study and development form a cycle. At first doing a preface study to find out a product that needed, it is rehabilitation based society model. Afterwards, the product is developed in a certain situation, validated, revised, tested, revised again until it is found the final product which is perfect.

Keywords: Rehabilitation Based Society, Disability, Village

Introduction

Contributions of the child with disability are part of Indonesia society who has position, rights, and similar obligation with other Indonesia society in all the aspect of life. The accomplishment similarity of position, rights, obligation, and ability improvement and child's role with disability is needed to effort that more adequate and integrated then continuity so that it could produce child's autonomous and prosperous with disability.

In fact, society still regards that child with disability and his or her family is a disgrace or something which is embarrassing. Child with disability is often faced on negative stigma and discrimination from other side. Even society and the family do not have enough understanding and capability so they look and treat child with disability badly. Society is the important part for taking in hand the problem of disability people beside family and government.

The country has main obligation to ensure, protect, and provide social service for all citizen as like education and health. In the same situation, family and society also have responsibility that equal relative. Ecological perspective make sure that family, society, village government, the government as mean the unsure that have big influence for child's need fulfillment with disability.

The condition of economy limitedness, the low of knowledge, and child family's education with disability caused family do not perform the function well. Society, as following neighborhood, social organization, and religion which is in the village is also low in doing their function, especially at the function of support and social participation. Village government, subdistrict to regency also have not a role actively for taking in hand the fulfillment of child's need with disability in the village area.

The program to serve disability people in the society created in rehabilitation based society or *Rehabilitasi Berbasis Masyarakat (RBM)*. Basically, this program concerns to the empowerment effort for all of potentials on the village. However, the society has not performed yet the function well. Especially for rehabilitation based society in filling the child's need with disability in the village. A lack function of rehabilitation based society in the fulfillment of child's need with disability becomes the main focus in this study. The effort to reveal it, the researcher means to analyze the model of rehabilitation based society which is effective as the effort in fulfillment of child's need with disability in the village could be achieved and improved.

Method

The objective of this study is formulating a model of rehabilitation based society as the effort of fulfillment for child's need with disability in the village area. To achieve the study objective, it will be conducted through three stages, namely: 1) preface study stage, which is the researcher collects the beginning information regarding objective condition on the field (empirically) and investigate it by doing literature study (theoretically), it will be done as the beginning data to make the summarization or draft model that developed; 2) model development stage, which is done Focus Group Discussion (FGD) and model validation by the experts through content validation and empirical validation so that it will be acquired model finishing, the method that is used in this stage is evaluative method; 3) implementation test stage, the model which has been developed and it has been passed through validation stage then it is implemented to be tested the performance, the method that is used in this stage is qualitative method.

Results and Discussion

Disability people is the term that used to physical defect accusative. According to *Undang-undang Republik Indonesia No. 19 Tahun 2011* regarding CRPD legalization asserts that:

Disability accusative is people who have physical limitedness, mental, intellectual, or sensory in the long period of time within interact to the environment and society behavior could fill the difficult obstacles to participate completely and effectively based on the similarity rights.

The child with disability faces many problems in several things, as the following:

The problem towards competition with people who do not get disability in all of the aspect, especially it refers to the opportunity in acquiring public service, education, and occupation. Then, the fact placed position of child with disability in the weakness or low condition so that it could be returned on the society stigma that disability accusative is people who are physical defect, not having self-reliance or depend on others.

This situation is exacerbated with not quite support from child with disability social surroundings, that caused child with disability become frustrated, fate, and apathetic to participate in the social life. It will effect that they tend to isolate themselves and live at themselves community.

At the other hand, the child with disability, because the lack is very susceptible towards wrong treatment, which is so bad or others from family, neighborhood, school, workplace, and so on. The treatment could be: exploitation (economy, sexual, wrong treatment or be breached the rights to get access of education, occupation, social service, etc.)

The child with disability faced discriminative treatment in many aspects of life. Meanwhile, the action from child with disability to do protection for themselves is still very limitedness. Then, for the attention and society generally towards child's need with disability.

Based on *Undang-Undang Republik Indonesia No. 4 Tahun 1997* regarding physical defect accusative, pasal 1 ayat 4, 5, 6, and 7 could be known about the need of disability people generally, namely:

The need of accessibility, is the need for disability people to make similarity chance in all the aspect of life.

The need of rehabilitation, is to re-functionalization and development for disability people who are able to perform the social function properly in social life.

The need of social assistance, is the need for disability people who are not able and it has the characteristic is non permanent in order they could increase their social prosperity.

The need of social prosperity care, is the need towards the protection and service effort which has continuity in order disability people could make a proper life.

Rehabilitation based society or *Rehabilitasi Berbasis Masyarakat* (RBM) according to Slamet (1998) is “Rehabilitation activity for disability people by doing the human power source. In other words, it is the rehabilitation activity is based on the principles of society empowerment”. Rehabilitation based society or RBM used the society role and family with the way of participating, acting, or mobilizing the society power source potential start from the process of plan, action, and reorientation for the activity.

Rehabilitation based society is an effort of social prosperity development for disability people that is conducted as a whole and fixed by the society element in the village through the training and recommendation in order disability people could perform their social function optimally in society. Rehabilitation is a re-functional and development process which is possible for disability people perform their social function in the social life. (*Kemensos RI No. 07/HUK/KBP/II/1984*).

Rehabilitation is an effort to recover people function which got derangement or obstacle, physically, mentally, psychologically, socially, and economically so that it could be the function again properly, by having support to the family role and community, and empower several initiative, potential, and society power source.

The main goal of rehabilitation in this study is to help disability people achieving optimal self-reliance physically, mentally, socially, vocationally, and economically accordance with the capability. Rehabilitation focus of this study is the individual holistically in ecological context, not only on the functional limitedness caused disability.

Holistic and ecological perspective include into the aspect of physical, mental, and individual's spiritual that related to the family, occupation and the whole surroundings as an unity. There are two rehabilitation based society or *Rehabilitasi Berbasis Masyarakat* (RBM) goals, namely:

To be able to make self-reliance for disability people that facing on the problem of social, family, and society which is they live. RBM tries to people with social problem has the access toward special service that they need, while they stay on the society and support them, then enjoy a life style as like other society. They participate in taking decision that influence themselves, family, and society.

For the education and society involvement in the integration for disability people with social problem. The activity of society education about people with social problem from RBM tries to supplying clear information about problem and the ways that possible to taking on handle it. Therefore, behavior, hope, society action will change, and could receive people with social problem as the part of society.

Rehabilitation based society is based on three main principles as follows:

Society knows and they could handle their problems. It is better than anyone. Society that called to perform preventive activities that evolved by themselves. The activity and changes will happen faster, if the society collaborate in the groups. Rehabilitation based institution needs the high cost. RBM is done through the effort of power source and society potential mobilization, and condition of people with social problem, then by doing coordination well with several sectors related to the whole service include into recommendation service for each sector. So that offering the normal environment. The real RBM is using wisdom, skill, and leadership of local society. Therefore, RBM prioritize the involvement of social organization, social regulation, figure of society, figure of religion, figure of youth, and the other society forum.

Conclusion

This study is very important which showed that child's condition with disability in the village. By using the effective model of rehabilitation based society could be beneficial toward the empowerment of child with disability envelop the function of physical, mental, social,

education, vocational, and effect to self-reliance and child's productive with disability. A good group work which is clear and intensive among child with disability, family, society, and government could form an effective model of RBM for the fulfillment effort child's need with disability in the village.

The discovery of this study is model of rehabilitation based society that will formulate and implement and it will be done the finishing final model as the fulfillment effort for child's need with disability. The scope area of this study is characteristic and social facts that related to local society empowerment. The study activity specifically will be focused on the aspects which is in the questions of study.

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